

THE EVOLUTION OF RUSSIAN AND EUROPEAN- ORIGIN ANTONYMS IN THE AZERBAIJANI LANGUAGE

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Abstract. Antonyms constitute an integral component of the lexical-semantic word groups of the Azerbaijani language. Genealogical and typological factors play a significant role in the formation of this group of words.

The oppositions and contradictions present in nature, society, human consciousness, and the inner world of individuals are inexhaustible. It is impossible to encompass all of them within the expressive means of a single language in the modern information age. Therefore, in order to convey concepts related to antonyms, there arises a need—under conditions of integration—to borrow appropriate words from other languages.

The contact of the Azerbaijani language with elements of Russian and European languages began in the 19th century. Borrowings from Russian and European languages have predominantly carried a formal character and have mainly possessed terminological features. At the same time, it can be observed that some of these words participate in the formation of antonymic pairs.

Keywords: Azerbaijani language, antonyms, semantic meaning, analysis

Annotatsiya. Antonimlar ozarbayjon tilining leksik-semantik soʻz guruhlarining ajralmas tarkibiy qismidir. Ushbu soʻzlar guruhining shakllanishida genealogik va tipologik omillar muhim rol oʻynaydi.

Tabiatda, jamiyatda, inson ongida hamda shaxsning ichki dunyosida mavjud boʻlgan qarama-qarshilik va ziddiyatlar nihoyasizdir. Zamonaviy axborot asrida ularning barchasini bitta tilning ifoda vositalari doirasida qamrab olish mumkin emas. Shu bois antonimlarga oid tushunchalarni ifodalash uchun integratsiya sharoitida boshqa tillardan mos soʻzlarni oʻzlashtirish zarurati yuzaga keladi.

Ozarbayjon tilining rus va Yevropa tillari unsurlari bilan aloqasi XIX asrdan boshlangan. Rus va Yevropa tillaridan kirib kelgan oʻzlashmalar asosan formal xarakterga ega boʻlib, koʻproq terminologik xususiyat kasb etgan. Shu bilan birga, ushbu soʻzlarning ayrimlari antonimik juftliklarning shakllanishida ham ishtirok etishi kuzatiladi.

Kalit soʻzlar: ozarbayjon tili, antonimlar, semantik maʼno, tahlil.

The emergence of antonymic words in a language is due to the inherently contradictory nature of the world that surrounds us. The linguistic expression of these contradictions, which form the basis of development, is reflected in antonyms. Therefore, antonyms constitute one of the most interesting parts of the lexical system [Jafarov, 2007, p. 35].

Russian- and European-origin borrowings used within antonymic pairs constitute a component of the general body of loanwords. Until the period of Azerbaijan's independence, a situation of bilingualism existed in the country. During that time, words entered the Azerbaijani language primarily through Russian, since Russian held a leading informational function. Under the dominance of Russian, the Azerbaijani

language was unable to independently access the international information space. Consequently, all new information, as well as the words and terms formed as means of expressing that information, entered Azerbaijani via Russian.

In the modern period, however, the Azerbaijani language has gained free integration opportunities within the international information space, and all universal innovations can now be reflected in this language without obstacles. V.A. Abdullayeva-Nabiyeva expresses accurate and noteworthy observations on this issue: “The increase and intensification of mass media, as well as the expansion of the coverage of the internet and communication technologies, activate the process of word borrowing and term formation in a language. Whereas in the previous century most borrowed terms were taken from Russian, in the modern period the tendency to move away from Russian has strengthened, and preference has been given to term exchange with European languages. Since the process of borrowing terms from European languages predominates today, their modes of assimilation also differ” [Abdullayeva-Nabiyeva, 2017, pp. 3–4].

These considerations characterize borrowed words and terms as a whole. Since the process by which new borrowings form antonymic series is not an exception at later stages, careful attention must be paid directly to the borrowed words and terms themselves. That is, as borrowings arrive together with new information, efforts should be made to ensure that they are used precisely in accordance with their designated meanings. In the process of creating antonyms, strengthening the mechanisms inherent in the internal resources of the native language should become a primary linguistic requirement.

Nevertheless, it should be noted that words that entered Azerbaijani from Russian or through Russian have been used in the language for many years and have therefore been able to become internal elements within antonymic pairs. Borrowed antonyms in Azerbaijani are not equal in terms of origin. In quantitative terms, antonym-containing words that entered Azerbaijani from Arabic and Persian exceed those borrowed from Russian and European languages. This is due to the fact that the contact of the Azerbaijani language with Arabic and Persian dates back much earlier. This contact, which began in the 7th century and continued until the early 20th century, resulted in the incorporation of words related to socio-political, poetic, cultural-domestic, social, economic, ideological, and other spheres into Azerbaijani. Some of these words were assimilated to the extent that they acquired a common-usage character. A certain portion of them also entered the homonymic, synonymic, and antonymic series of the Azerbaijani language.

Contact between Azerbaijani and Russian and European languages began in the 19th century. During this period, many words were less fully assimilated compared to Arabic and Persian borrowings and thus entered common vocabulary to a lesser extent. Consequently, these words have been represented at a limited level within lexical-semantic word groups, including antonyms. Borrowings from Russian and European languages have mostly carried a formal character and primarily possessed terminological features. Alongside this, it is also observed that some of these words participate in the formation of antonymic pairs.

Although in the modern period the Azerbaijani language has been able to create an environment of free integration with European languages, special attention is given to the use of words from these languages that have recently become widespread,

particularly in advertising. In addition, as a result of integration with European languages, a group of words related to informativeness is used in the language of the press. While these words, in certain cases, participate in the formation of synonymic series, they do not demonstrate any significant progress in the formation of antonymic series. However, it cannot be claimed that, under the conditions of inevitable globalization, words of European origin have no role whatsoever in the formation of antonymic series in the Azerbaijani language.

Thus, the words of Russian and European origin that participate in the formation of antonymic series in the Azerbaijani language can be summarized according to the following classification based on their structural composition. The examples have been selected from H. Hasanov's dictionary of antonyms [Hasanov, 2007, p. 144]. In these antonymic pairs, both components are expressed by words of European origin. The following examples may be cited:

Both components of French origin:

altruist (one who forgets personal interests and cares for others) – *egoist* (self-centered, one who does not value others and considers oneself superior);

major (a musical mode in which the chord is built on a major scale) – *minor* (a musical mode in which the chord is built on a minor scale).

Both components of Greek origin:

analysis (examination) – *synthesis* (result, summary; a method of determining the relationships among elements obtained through analysis and deriving a general conclusion from them);

anarchy (lawlessness, disorder, absence of authority, rejection of all forms of power) – *democracy* (a form of governance serving the interests of the people);
archaism (a word that has become obsolete and fallen out of use) – *neologism* (a newly coined word).

Both components of Latin origin:

object (target) – *subject* (that which is spoken about, the object of judgment);
active (energetic, dynamic, diligent) – *passive* (inactive, indifferent, motionless);
maximum (the greatest amount, the highest degree) – *minimum* (the smallest amount, the lowest degree);

concreteness (precision, clarity) – *abstractness* (imprecision, abstraction).

One component of Greek origin and the other of Arabic origin:
anarchy (disorder, lawlessness) – *order* (observance of required norms);
democratic (serving the interests of the people; democratic forces) – *reactionary* (retrogressive, opposing, destructive);

comedy (laughter, farce) – *tragedy* (disaster, misfortune);
barbarism (cruelty, destructiveness, inhumanity) – *humanity* (humanism, kindness);
despot (cruel, merciless ruler) – *merciful* (gentle, kind).

One component of Latin origin and the other of Arabic origin:
collective (common, shared by all) – *individual* (belonging to a single person);
form (external appearance) – *content* (inner essence).

One component of Latin origin and the other of Greek origin:
real (true, corresponding to reality) – *fantastic* (extraordinary, imaginary, unbelievable);

nihilist (one who denies everything and accepts nothing) – *cosmopolitan* (one who considers everything as belonging to oneself and claims foreign cultural, social, and other traditions as one's own).

One component of French origin and the other of Arabic origin: *antique* (ancient, unusual, rare, elegant, valuable) – *modern* (present-day, contemporary, ordinary in appearance).

Both components of English origin:

export (goods sent abroad) – *import* (goods brought in from abroad).

One component of English origin and the other of Latin origin: *start* (beginning, the starting moment of a sports competition) – *final* (end, the concluding stage of a sports competition).

One component of Greek origin and the other of Azerbaijani origin:

abnormal (not normal, unusual, mentally deficient) – *intelligent* (normal, sound-minded).

The contrasts and contradictions present in nature, society, human consciousness, and the inner world of the individual are inexhaustible. It is not possible to accommodate all of them within the expressive means of a single language in the modern information age. Therefore, in order to convey concepts related to antonyms, there arises a need, under conditions of integration, to borrow appropriate words from other languages as well.

The key point is that the inclusion of borrowed words in the system of Azerbaijani antonyms cannot be regarded as a permanent process. As the internal potential of the native language develops and becomes aligned with the growing flow of information, the probability of forming new words in the native language to express new concepts continues to increase. Antonymic pairs are not excluded from this process, and real opportunities emerge in the language for the creation of new means of expression.

References:

1. Abdullayeva-Nabiyeva, V. A. *Directions of Development of Terminological Vocabulary in the Modern Azerbaijani Language*: Abstract of the dissertation for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy in Philology. Baku, 2017, 32 p.
2. Jafarov, S. *Modern Azerbaijani Language. Lexicon* (in 4 parts). Part 2. Baku: Sharq-Qarb, 2007, 192 p.
3. Hasanov, H. *Dictionary of Antonyms of the Azerbaijani Language*. Baku: Sharq-Qarb, 2007, 144 p.